

Institute collaboration) were tested in seven trials against check Co 43. Cultures 433A-R5 and 433A-R6 performed better than Co 43 during kar (Jul-Oct) season (8.8 and 11.4% yield increase) (see table).

Culture 433A-R6 was photoperiod

insensitive (duration 134–137 d); duration fluctuated 11–20 d in other cultures. All cultures are semidwarf (plant height 57–76 cm) and all have 6.9–7.7 panicles/hill. Grain in 6 cultures is short and bold; in 433A-R6, it is long and slender. Rice color is white.

Culture 433A-R1 is resistant to blast (Bl) and rice tungro virus (RTV); 433A-R5 is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to RTV and bacterial blight (BB); 433A-R6 is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to RTV, BB, and brown spot. □

Performance of anther culture-derived rice lines at Coimbatore, India, 1982-83 to 1986-87.^a

Culture	Mean grain yield (t/ha)				Productivity (kg/d)	Duration (d)				Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	1000-grain wt (g)
	Kar	Cold weather	Navarai	Overall mean		Kar	Cold weather	Navarai	Mean			
433A-R1	5.2	4.5	5.9	5.2	37.1	141	148	132	140	76	7.1	19.6
433A-R2	5.0	4.5	5.5	5.0	35.8	136	150	132	139	72	7.3	20.9
433A-R3	5.3	4.1	4.8	4.8	34.1	139	151	134	141	75	7.7	19.4
433A-R4	5.2	4.2	5.5	5.0	35.8	138	151	132	140	69	6.9	19.0
433A-R5	5.4	4.9	5.8	5.4	38.6	137	152	132	140	75	7.5	18.8
433A-R6	5.6	4.6	5.7	5.3	39.1	137	136	134	136	57	7.3	19.0
433A-R7	5.1	4.8	4.7	4.9	34.9	138	149	134	140	76	7.1	19.0
Co 43 (check)	5.0	4.9	5.9	5.22	38.4	139	141	130	136	74	7.2	20.0

^aKar = Jul-Oct, navarai = Feb-Apr.

***Oryza nivara* sources of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) in rice**

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Cytoplasmic diversity is an important problem in hybrid rice breeding and production. Only a few CMS sources are being used in China, making hybrid rice potentially vulnerable to a disease or insect epidemic.

To find new sources for hybrid rice breeding and to study the cytogenic interaction in *Oryza* spp., we have used *O. nivara* introduced from IRRI (acc. 101508 and 101466) as donors of CMS cytoplasm in crosses with one set of cultivars. So far, we have developed four CMS lines—Chao Yang 1A (indica), Zhen Shan 97A (indica), Nan Jin 56A (japonica), and Rei-Min A (japonica)—that have the cytoplasm of *O. nivara* acc. 101508.

Preliminary studies show no significant difference between Zhen Shan 97A (nivara cytoplasm) and Zhen Shan 97A (WA cytoplasm) in agrocharacter, floral characters, and pollen fertility (Table 1), and in cytogenic interaction (Table 2). The two

Table 1. Comparison of N-Zhen Shan 97A with W-Zhen Shan 97A. Puzhou, China, 1987.

CMS A-line	Days to 50% heading	Height (cm)	Panicle exertion (cm)	Exserted stigma (%)	Pollen fertility (%)	
					Typical abortive	Round abortive
N-Zhen Shan 97A	68.5	57.0	-6.1	25.9	92.1	7.9
W-Zhen Shan 97A	70.0	56.3	-5.8	24.1	89.3	10.7

Table 2. Pollen fertility of F₁ progenies.^a Hainan, China, 1988.

Male parent	Plants (no.)	Female parent								
		N-Zhen Shan 97A				W-Zhen Shan 97A				
		F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				
F	PF	PS	CS	F	PF	PS	CS			
IR22	20	16	4	0	0	20	17	3	0	0
IR24	20	20	0	0	0	20	18	2	0	0
Ming 63	20	19	1	0	0	18	18	0	0	0
Taiyin 1	18	16	1	1	0	20	18	2	0	0
Milyang 46	20	18	2	0	0	20	19	1	0	0
IR46826B	20	0	0	3	17	20	0	0	2	18
IR46827B	20	0	0	1	19	20	0	0	1	19
IR46828B	20	0	0	4	16	20	0	0	2	18
Hong 410	20	0	3	13	4	20	0	4	12	4

^aPollen fertility classes: F = fertile, 91–100% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 51–90% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 6–50% pollen fertility; CS = completely sterile, 0–5% pollen fertility.

CMS sources seem to be genetically similar.

In a crossing experiment based on F₁ pollen fertility, IR22, IR24, Ming 63, Taiyin 1, IR1055, Yin Ni Ai He,

Milyang 23, and Milyang 46 were classified as effective restorers; Hong 410 as a partial maintainer; and IR46826B, IR46827B, and IR46828B as complete maintainers to both A-lines.